

One Belt One Road - Broadening a in the MERCOSUR and European Union

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Despite the focus of the New Silk Road project being Eurasia (Europe + Asia) and Africa, China has left it open for anyone interested.

The Chinese project of globalization by the - One Belt One Road - the Chinese globalization project, set up by the new Silk Road, is linked to other regional organizations such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (OCX), Asian Economic Union (UEE) and ASEAN.

OCX, expanded with India and Pakistan beyond 4 observer states (Afghanistan, Belarus, Mongolia) and 6 dialogue partners - Azerbaijan, Armenia, Cambodia, Nepal, Turkey, Sri Lanka.

Fonte: Shanghai Cooperation Organization

The Chinese initiative of the New Silk Road - OBOR - One Belt , One Road is a mechanism for the consolidation of its projects in Eurasia having at its core China - the main emerging power, and Russia, still a geopolitical power (territorial, military and energy), this initiative Beijing involves about 65 countries that collectively represent more than 30% of global GDP, 62% of the population and 75% of known energy reserves.

China brought new challenges to South America countries and other European countries like Portugal and Spain and also the acceleration and expansion of global trends that changed the scenario for the evolution of bilateral relations.

At the end of 2020, the deepening of trade ties and expectations in the area of investment and technological cooperation between Brazil and Portugal and China occur at the time when the ambitions of political dialogue are being resized and the uncertainties regarding the future.

Chile, for example, present at the International Silk Road Forum, in 2017 former President Michelle Bachelet, said in her voice that this is the biggest economic project currently under debate, "Suitable for new horizons".

It is worth remembering that China is the main Brazilian economic partner. It is the country to which Brazil exports the most and the second most important, behind only the USA.

Chinese FDI into the EU the figure is almost €120 billion. EU FDI in China remains relatively modest with respect to the size and the potential of the Chinese economy.

As regards investment, the EU-China Comprehensive Agreement on Investment (CAI) will be the most ambitious agreement that China has ever concluded with a third country. In addition to rules against the forced transfer of technologies, CAI will also be the first agreement to deliver on obligations for the behaviour of state-owned enterprises, comprehensive transparency rules for subsidies and commitments related to sustainable development.

The CAI will ensure that EU investors achieve better **access** to a fast growing 1.4 billion consumer market, and that they compete on a better level playing field in China. This is important for the global competitiveness and the future growth of EU industry.

Ambitious opening by China to European investments

An agenda from other countries initially out of the OBOR – One Belt One Road to China in the area of infrastructure requires a long-term vision and involves the application of recent experience and common sense to resolve issues such as mitigating information asymmetries, approaching the risk matrix and creating the environment favourable.

The main challenge is how to promote, in the new PPP ecosystem evolving in the country, a timely and quality dialogue between Chinese investors, private investors, public and private banks and governments.

Possibly there will be a decrease in the Chinese ambition for projects abroad with the uncertainty of the international political environment.

This increases the importance of smooth political dialogue and clear signals to investors.

Others countries planning can benefit from an expanded dialogue with companies, academia and think tanks, including the identification of topics for contracting studies and the permanent holding of seminar agendas.

There is great potential for the mobilization of human and technical resources that can contribute to the construction of a strategy and government plans.

This reflection should not only occur in the public sector or focused on it, but also in the business sector, universities and the third sector, which will contribute to raising the quality and consistency of a national strategy and the respective sector and business strategies.

This work presents a framework and bases for a strategy with a view to contributing others countries out of the initial OBOR Map to a comprehensive and long-term reflection on China.

Firstly, the CAI binds China's liberalisation of investments over the last 20 years and, in that way, it prevents backsliding. This makes the conditions of market access for EU companies clear and independent of China's internal policies. It also allows the EU to resort to the dispute resolution mechanism in CAI in case of breach of commitments.

In addition, the EU has negotiated further and new market access openings and commitments such as the elimination of quantitative restrictions, equity caps or joint venture requirements in a number of sectors. These are restrictions that severely hamper the activities of our companies in China. The overall package is far more ambitious than what China has committed to before.

On the EU side, the market is already open and largely committed for services sectors under the General Agreement on Trade in Services (GATS). EU sensitivities, such as in the field of energy, agriculture, fisheries, audio-visual, public services, etc. are all preserved in CAI.

Examples of market access commitments by China:

- **Manufacturing:** China has made comprehensive commitments with only very limited exclusions (in particular, in sectors with significant overcapacity). In terms of the level of ambition, this would match the EU's openness. Roughly half of EU FDI is in the manufacturing sector (e.g. transport and telecommunication equipment, chemicals, health equipment etc.). China has not made such far-reaching market access commitments with any other partner.
- **Automotive sector:** China has agreed to remove and phase out joint venture requirements. China will commit market access for new energy vehicles.
- **Financial services:** China had already started the process of gradually liberalising the financial services sector and will grant and commit to keep that opening to EU investors. Joint venture requirements and foreign equity caps have been removed for banking, trading in securities and insurance (including reinsurance), as well as asset management.
- **Health (private hospitals):** China will offer new market opening by lifting joint venture requirements for private hospitals in key Chinese cities, including Beijing, Shanghai, Tianjian, Guangzhou and Shenzhen .
- **R&D (biological resources):** China has not previously committed openness to foreign investment in R&D in biological resources. China has agreed not to introduce new restrictions and to give to the EU any lifting of current restrictions in this area that may happen in the future.
- **Telecommunication/Cloud services:** China has agreed to lift the investment ban for cloud services. They will now be open to EU investors subject to a 50% equity cap.
- **Computer services:** China has agreed to bind market access for computer services - a significant improvement from the current situation. Also, China will include a 'technology neutrality' clause, which would ensure that equity caps imposed for value-added telecom services will not be applied to other services such as financial, logistics, medical etc. if offered online.
- **International maritime transport:** China will allow investment in the relevant land-based auxiliary activities, enabling EU companies to invest without restriction in cargo-handling, container depots and stations, maritime agencies, etc. This will allow EU companies to organise a full range of multi-modal door-to-door transport, including the domestic leg of international maritime transport.
- **Air transport-related services:** While the CAI does not address traffic rights because they are subject to separate aviation agreements, China will open up in the key areas of computer reservation systems, ground handling and selling and marketing services. China has also removed its minimum capital

requirement for rental and leasing of aircraft without crew, going beyond GATS.

- **Business services:** China will eliminate joint venture requirements in real estate services, rental and leasing services, repair and maintenance for transport, advertising, market research, management consulting and translation services, etc.
- **Environmental services:** China will remove joint venture requirements in environmental services such as sewage, noise abatement, solid waste disposal, cleaning of exhaust gases, nature and landscape protection, sanitations and other environmental services.
- **Construction services:** China will eliminate the project limitations currently reserved in their GATS commitments.
- **Employees of EU investors:** Managers and specialists of EU companies will be allowed to work up to three years in Chinese subsidiaries, without restrictions such as labour market tests or quotas. Representatives of EU investors will be allowed to visit freely prior to making an investment.

Some criticism that the New Silk Road project has received are:

- Open to anyone who is interested, it is an opportunity for structural development like few others, with an abundance of resources, based on the successful Chinese experience - especially in works in Asia and Africa, and with the possibility of becoming the largest infrastructure network in the history of humanity. In addition to this, there is a discourse of international cooperation, without military use.
- If consolidated, the route can lead to the creation of new markets and free trade zones, generate new zones for the supply and distribution of products, facilitate travel by land and sea and provide great advances in the integration of its participants and their populations.
- With the withdrawal of the United States from the Trans-Pacific Agreement and its virtual weakening, the project serves as an alternative for countries in the Pacific region.
- With the possibility of an overland route, providing another outlet beyond the Malacca Strait, the project could reduce tensions in the South China Sea region, contributing to stability in the region. In turn, some of the criticisms of the project are:
 - Some claim that the project is a discreet way of expanding Chinese influence across the globe. The strong commercial and economic ties could increase China's control, especially over the poorest regions, in addition to increasing its power over Eurasia, a geopolitically strategic region.

- The works, in large part, would end up in the hands of Chinese construction companies, being a way of projecting them to the detriment of local construction companies. As a result, it could be difficult to deal with local labor.

- It is questioned to what extent the debt of partners in the project can be remedied. African countries and historically conflicting Asians, such as Pakistan, would fit into this. In the same way, it is questioned to what extent the resources directed to the project will in fact be applied by its recipients and the security of carrying out the works.

- The harmony around the project is also questioned. The non-accession of India, the second most populous country in the world and extremely important in the Asian region, largely because of possible works in Kashmir - a region divided and in dispute between India, Pakistan and China - reinforces this. Possible competition with Russian interests in the region is also raised.

- The financial viability of the project is also put in check. More annual resources would be needed for its consolidation than currently existing ones and many of the areas through which the route would pass are areas of conflict, which would make it difficult to carry out and preserve works.

- Initially, the main source of planned investment was the Silk Road Fund, founded in December 2014, by 4 actors:

- State Administration of Foreign Policy (responsible for 65% of the investment);
- China Investment Corporation (15%);
- China Development Bank (5%);
- China Export and Import Bank (15%).

- A total of US \$ 40 billion was expected to come out of this fund for investments in medium and long-term works.

- In addition to this amount, at the 2017 International Silk Road Forum, the Chinese government announced an increase of US \$ 70 billion in its investment in the route (approximately US \$ 15 billion from the government and US \$ 55 from the two banks involved).

- There is also the possibility of financing from international banks. In his 2014 speech, Xi stated that he also intends to use resources from the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank (AIIB), the BRICS Development Bank and the World Bank.

The Portuguese Study Case

Regarding Portugal, 17 sectors are dealt with that give rise to the memoranda that the Portuguese government signed with China in 2018:

- Cooperation in the framework of the new maritime silk route - “One Belt, One Route”;

- Cooperation on trade and services (such as transport, tourism and technology); - programming of cultural festivals;
- Implementation of the Science and Technology partnership; - implementation of STARLAB - cooperation in the field of water;
- memorandum of understanding between COFCO International and AICEP for the creation of a global COFCO service in Matosinhos, with the creation of 150 jobs; - cooperation in terms of corporate social responsibility, namely in the field of culture, sustainable development, innovation and R&D; - actions between State Grid and REN, for the construction of new North - South and West - East railways - implementation by MEO and Huawei of antennas at the TN level for 5G emissions;
- Export of Portuguese table grapes to China;
- Follow up of the BCP agreement and Union Pay, for the issuance of credit cards from the Chinese financial services company that leads electronic payments in China;
- Production by the Media Group of China and RTP for the joint production of documentaries;
- Establishment of the Confúcio Institute at the University of Porto; - Creation of a Chinese studies center at the University of Coimbra;
- Execution by CGD and Bank of China of issuing Panda Bonds, related to the issuance of public debt in Renminbi.

Actions to be developed in 2021 by Portugal and China

- New issuance of debt securities Known as “Panda” bonds, Mário Centeno made Portugal the first country in Europe to issue these bonds in the amount of 2 billion yuan (US \$ 289 million) in bonds maturing in three years. This operation should be repeated in 2021 during the Portuguese presidency of the EU in order to convince member countries to proceed in the same way
- The China Construction Third Engineering Bureau Group (CCTEBG), which is part of the China State Construction Engineering Corporation (CSCEC), was recently in Lisbon and Porto, to expand the Leixões and Sines terminals and to build railways for loading and unloading as well as quick customs clearance through a simplex system. An investment of 642 million euros (US \$ 701.9 million) is earmarked for this purpose and operations in the port and adjacent facilities are carried out by COSCO Shipping
- Transformation in Leixões of the refineries into an LNG storage park by a Portuguese company to be hired by China Construction Third Engineering Bureau Group (CCTEBG), with the company Mota Engil being considered as trustworthy.

- As required by AICEP Global Parques, a € 640 million Chinese-built container port is integrated into the key project at Belt & Road. - Details of the agreements signed at the Queluz Palace, in a ceremony chaired by the Portuguese Prime Minister, António Costa, and by the Chinese head of state, Xi Jinping, by a bilateral Portugal

- China commission. - I work for a Portuguese and Chinese bilateral commission of the "21st Century Maritime Silk Road" protocols signed by the Minister of Foreign Affairs, Augusto Santos Silva, and by the director of the National Development and Reform Commission (with ministerial status), He Lifeng.

- Development of entrepreneurial actions covering a wide range of sectors, with an emphasis on connectivity and electric mobility. - Appropriation for the purchase of lithium mineral deposits in Portugal.

- Chinese political and military news Portuguese TV which is still in choice for investment as a shareholder or paid permission broadcast time TV

In conclusion

The systemic transition pushes the world towards shocks in multiple dimensions. The conservative inflection, the international politics of the United States of America, the multiple multiplication of failed states, the humanitarian and migratory crises, the strengthening of xenophobia and centrifugal forces in Europe, the growth of tensions in several Asia-Pacific regions increase the risk of military escalations exacerbated by a global economic crisis that started in 2008 at the epicentre of the system. The intertwining of the new scientific and technological potentials and the new configurations of power that emerges around the Russian bell axis and the New Silk Road.

The safety challenges of "One Belt - One Road - depend on the accommodation between the established power - the USA - and the other emerging power - China.

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